

METALIZED CARBON FIBERS FOR SOLDERABLE AND WEAR-RESISTANT COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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1 Introduction

Coated carbon fibers provide a high potential as carrier of functions in composite materials for the application in lightweight constructions. For instance, layers of low-melting metals like zinc carry the function of an adhesion promoter for wear-resistant top coatings on carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP's) [1]. High melting coating materials like copper are useful for joining zones to solder metals with composites which will substitute the common joining techniques for CFRP's like rivet and screw connections [2, 3]. The generation of metallic coatings on carbon fiber rovings by means of electrodeposition techniques [4, 5, 6, 7] was studied. The obtained coatings were examined and a wide spectrum of influencing factors of the coating process was identified. Further future objective of the obtained results is to deduce working parameters of a continuous coating process in order to create adhesive joining zones on CFRPs.

2 Experimental

2.1 Preparation of the substrates

Carbon fiber rovings of the type Toho Teijin Tenax-E HTA 40 E13 3K were cut into segments of approximately 120 mm length and crimped at one end by a ferrule.

Furthermore, non-woven fabrics of the (type 756 by C. Cramer Weberei GmbH & Co. KG with Toho Teijin Tenax HTA 40 E13 3K fibers) and woven fabrics (160 g m⁻² type by R&G Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH with Toho Teijin Tenax HTA 40 E13 3K fibers) were cut into segments of 40 x 60 mm to coat the top layer of the carbon fibers. Desizing was carried out by immersing the carbon fibers in acetone for 60 minutes.

To produce CFRP, the carbon fiber substrates were infiltrated with epoxy resin "L" and hardener "EPH 161" both by R&G Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH with a resin/hardener ratio of 100/25 in an aluminum laminating form. Therefore, the aluminum laminating form was prepared by spraying a silicone-free releasing agent with an operating temperature of up to 120 °C. After the lamination process the samples were cured under preload for 24 hours at room temperature.

Samples for joining experiments were grinded at the surface to remove epoxy matrix material from the top layer of carbon fibers.

2.2 Metal deposition on substrates

The prepared substrates were immersed in a specific electrolyte for zinc, tin or copper at a temperature 25±1 °C. An insulating frame construction made of acrylic glass was used to coat the substrates on a length of 70 mm homogenously. The distance between substrate and both anodes was set to 3 cm each. The electrodeposition on carbon fiber rovings and CFRP was carried out under variation of the process parameters like current density from 0.25 to 1.5 A/dm² which was adjusted by a power supply unit Beha Uniwatt NG 304 or plating time from 5 to 60 minutes. The agitation of the electrolyte was secured by a laboratory mixer IKA C MAG HS 7.

The coated samples were rinsed with distilled water and ethanol. Subsequently, drying at 60 °C for 4 hours in a vacuum compartment dryer finalized the coating process.

2.3 Soldering of single lap joints

In further joining experiments single lap joints were produced by soldering a zinc- or copper-plated CFRP with a steel sheet. The overlapping area was

10 mm width, the length varied between 10 and 15 mm. Because of its excellent wetting on the substrate materials and the low operating temperature a tin-lead solder (Sn60Pb40) was used. For pre-wetting, the single sheets were first dipped into liquid flux (Kolo 400-25 by Stannol) and afterwards immersed into the liquid solder ($T = 220\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $t = 15\text{ s}$). The lap joints were soldered by using the joining equipment in Fig. 1. Thereby, the sheets were pressed together with a force of 20 N. The operating temperature of $220\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was controlled by a thermocouple.

2.4 Characterization methods

Contact angle measurements were performed to determine the solderability of the samples. Therefore, rovings of metal-coated carbon fibers were immersed 5 mm deep in molten solder for 3 s and cleaned in ethanol with ultrasonic for 10 s after solidification. For copper and zinc coating a tin/silver SnAg5 solder was used at a temperature of $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Tin specimens were soldered at $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a low-melting Reginox Universal-Solder 65. To prevent oxidation of the surface of molten solder, it was wetted with the flux Kolo 400-25 by Stannol. Pre-treatment of the specimens for the hindrance of oxidation or descaling was realized as follows: a) copper was wetted with flux Kolo 400-25 by Stannol, b) zinc was immersed in hydrochloric acid (3.7 %) for 3 s and wetted with flux Fontargen F600 S15 equally c) tin was treated.

Four specimens of each type of metal coating were prepared by longitudinal cutting to determine the average values of the contact angle via optical microscope Olympus GX51.

Mechanical characterization of the metal-coated carbon fiber rovings was carried out by tensile tests in dependence on test specification DIN EN 1007-5. Samples of 20 mm long rovings were soldered on a steel sheet with a defined joining-length of 1–3 mm. The other end of the roving was glued on a mounting device to fit the sample in the tensile testing machine manufactured by Kammrath & Weiss GmbH. The feed rate was adjusted to $20\text{ }\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$. After the tensile test the joining zone of each sample was polished as cross-section to determine the number of fibers which are passing through the joint (Fig. 2). The adhesive strength of the coating is calculated by use of the measured

parameters (# ... number of fibers; L_{join} ... joining length; $d_f = 7\text{ }\mu\text{m}$... diameter of fiber) into equation 1.

$$\tau_{adh} = \frac{F_{max}}{\# * L_{join} * d_f * \pi} \quad (1)$$

Mechanical characterization of single joint laps was realized by tensile shear tests according to DIN EN 1465 on a tensile/compression-module (Kammrath & Weiss GmbH). The feed rate was set at $2\text{ }\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Electrodeposition Experiments

The electrodeposition process is influenced by the kind of metal to be deposited. The coatings on the carbon fiber rovings showed a specific morphology for each of the obtained layer (Fig. 3–5). A zinc coating for example (Fig. 3) leads to an inhomogeneous distributed layer-thickness. In Fig. 3 the coated fibers show the most homogeneous result by applying a cathodic current density of 1 A dm^{-2} for 15 minutes. Higher and also lower current densities will lead to uncoated fibers in the center of the roving. At high current densities an increasing occurrence of gaseous hydrogen is observed. This side reaction can also be verified by a lowering of the electrical yield from 100 % down to 90 %. At lower current densities the decreasing throwing power of the electrolyte is the reason for a less homogeneous coating.

Tin coated carbon fibers show a typical pronounced dendritic growth behavior which gets broadened by increasing the cathodic current density. To get maximum dendrite-free and homogenous coated rovings a low cathodic current density of 0.25 A dm^{-2} must be applied during 15 minutes of the plating process (Fig. 4).

Copper-plated carbon fibers show a homogenous distributed thickness of the coating. A cathodic current density from 0.25 to 1.5 A dm^{-2} leads to such a result. The following experiments for mechanical characterization were performed with samples which are electroplated at 1 A dm^{-2} for 5 minutes (Fig. 5). Carbon fiber fabrics can be metalized analogous to carbon fiber rovings. Here, mainly the outer C-fibers of the fabric are completely coated with copper. Thereby, the metallization of the fiber decreases

with increasing distance from the fabrics surface (Fig. 6).

The electrolyte cannot penetrate in the lower C-fiber fabric layers and only the outer layers are metalized. When using copper paste as a contact agent between fabric and conductive clamp thicker layers (without paste: 3–4 μm ; with paste: 7–10 μm) are deposited (Fig. 7).

Carbon fiber woven is a quite better conducting carbon substrate, which can easily be coated with copper by electrodeposition technique (Fig. 8–10). Carbon fiber woven is coated at the outer layers, because the electrolyte cannot penetrate the woven. However, similar to other electroplating processes a structure-property relationship between metallization conditions and layer thickness can be detected. A longer coating time leads to thicker coatings. At 15 minutes coating time, the layer thickness is about 2–10 μm , at 30 minutes it amounts to 15–25 μm and at 45 minutes to 20–50 μm .

3.2 Wetting Experiments

Prior to the joining experiments the contact angle between metallic coating and solder material was examined to secure their solderability (Fig. 11). Coated carbon fibers with copper and zinc exhibit a similar contact angle (15°) to the corresponding metal wires with solder, which are around 20° . Tin-coated carbon fibers with their distinct dendrites get well-wetted by solder but the measured contact angle is only 5° . All evaluated metal wire materials are known as joining partners with a well solderability. Based on this fact it can be argued that also the coated carbon fibers with similar contact angles can secure the necessary grade of solderability.

3.3 Adhesive Strength Experiments

To determine the adhesive strength of the metal coating on electroplated carbon fibers the described tensile test was performed. Typical force-distance diagrams were obtained (Fig. 12). The first low slope of the curve mainly shows the elasticity of the soldered and glued joints of the sample. At the plateau-shaped progression (at a force around 50 N) the successive collapse of single fibers is observed. This fact is also verified by optical monitoring of the

specimen during the tensile test (Fig. 13). Further pulling causes a low decrease in measured force which is ascribed to a continued force fit by still intact carbon fibers. In cause of this behavior the carbon fibers are the weakest part of the sample. Both soldering zone and galvanic coating show a higher loadability than the fibers. This behavior is found for all examined types of metal coatings.

Inserting the measured maximum force into equation 1 results the minimum adhesive strength of the coating on the carbon fiber (Fig. 14). All coatings show higher adhesive strengths than the calculated data of around 2 MPa. The significant parameter which has to be adjusted is the joining length L_{join} . By reducing this size a higher tensile strength can be reached at the same load on the sample. The observed interface between carbon fiber and metal coating will be characterized in more detail. In further experiments possibilities for the needed reduction of the joining length by using additional soldering materials like solder mask will be expedient.

3.4 Joining Experiments

Fig. 15 shows the possibility to solder a single lap joint of CFRP with metalized carbon fibers and steel sheets. For copper-coated specimens the cross-section in Fig. 16 exhibits a continuous formation of a diffusion zone between copper/solder and solder/steel. The fracture pattern of the copper-coated sample illustrates the strong interface between the copper layer and the fiber. The breakage runs in half each along the interface between fiber and coating as well as within the solder (Fig. 17). While the tensile shear strength of the copper-coated samples is 4.0 ± 0.1 MPa, it is less than 1 MPa of the zinc coated ones.

Only a few of the zinc-containing lap joints could be tested because of the poor joining result. Most of them broke by removing them from the joining equipment. The poor bonding is caused by the disability of the flux to remove the zinc oxides sufficiently before soldering. The relatively low adhesive strengths of the copper samples reveal a weak fiber/coating-bonding. Prospective, the adhesion could be increased by ensuring the usage of fully coated fibers (e.g. Fig. 5) instead of only top-coated ones on the surface of the CFRP (e.g. Fig. 18).

4 Conclusions

In first experiments carbon fiber reinforced polymers were produced by impregnating the carbon fibers with an epoxy resin. Furthermore, the carbon fiber surface was removed by grinding the epoxy resin layer. To avoid problems with brittle surfaces or oxidation processes, the accessible carbon fibers were metalized by galvanic copper deposition (Fig. 18).

The copper layer enables the possibility to solder the CFRP. In this context, the CFRP was jointed to steel (Fig. 16). The adhesion between the layers of the composite material was analyzed by measuring the tensile shear strength. If homogeneous coated fibers are needed for further application of the CFRP the coating process should be upstream of textile processing preferably.

Those promising results form the basis for a modular approach to produce tailored CFRP. Therefore, a continuous coating procedure for different metals (Zn, Sn, Cu, ...) has to be investigated. Thus, a large quantity of functional coated carbon fiber can be provided in the future.

Finally, structure-property relationships between the metal, the thickness of the metal layer and the adhesion were determined to validate the mechanical performance of the CFRP as well as the soldered composite material performance. Further future objective of the obtained results is to deduce working parameters of a continuous coating process in order to create adhesive joining zones on CFRPs.

Figures

Fig.1. Scheme of the joining equipment for soldering metallized CFRP to steel sheets under pressure using a heating plate.

Fig.2. Microscopic image of a cross-section through the joining zone of a soldered copper plated carbon fiber roving for determination of the shear tensile strength of the coating.

Fig.3. Microscopic image of a cross-section of galvanic coated carbon fiber roving with zinc.

Fig.4. Microscopic image of a cross-section of galvanic coated carbon fiber roving with tin.

Fig.5. Microscopic image of a cross-section of galvanic coated carbon fiber roving with copper.

Fig.6. Microscopic image of a cross-section of galvanic coated unidirectional carbon fiber layers with copper. The carbon fibers were contacted by a wet sponge.

Fig.7. Microscopic image of a cross-section of galvanic coated unidirectional carbon fiber layers with copper. The carbon fibers were contacted by a paste of copper.

Fig.8. Microscopic image of a cross-section of 15 minutes galvanic coated carbon fiber woven with copper. The carbon fiber woven was contacted by a paste of copper.

Fig.9. Microscopic image of a cross-section of 30 minutes galvanic coated carbon fiber woven with copper. The carbon fiber woven was contacted by a paste of copper.

Fig.10. Microscopic image of a cross-section of 45 minutes galvanic coated carbon fiber woven with copper. The carbon fiber woven was contacted by a paste of copper.

Fig.11. Comparison of the contact angles of copper, zinc and tin plated carbon fibers and the corresponding metal wires with solder material.

Fig.12. Force-distance diagram of a soldered copper plated carbon fiber roving for determination of the shear tensile strength of the coating.

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Fig.13. Photograph of a soldered copper plated carbon fiber roving after tensile test.

Fig.14. Minimum adhesive strengths of metal coatings on carbon fibers.

Fig.15. Soldered single lap joint of a CFRP with metal coated carbon fibers and a steel sheet.

Fig.16. Microscopic image of a cross- section in longitudinal direction of the material in Fig.18. soldered with Sn60Pb40 to steel.

Fig.17. Fracture patterns of a soldered CFRP with metal-coated carbon fibers and steel sheet after tensile shear tests. The breakage runs half inside the solder and half in the interface copper/fiber.

Fig.18. Microscopic image of a cross-section of a carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin with a copper coating on the carbon fiber surface.

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